

A Fast Procedure to Estimate the Prevailing Rupture Propagation Direction And How It Applies to the 2016-2017 Central Italy Seismic Sequence

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ABSTRACT

- ❖ We present a new approach aimed to generalize the statistical procedure proposed by Calderoni et al., (2017) to estimate the prevailing direction of rupture propagation in a given region during a seismic sequence. The method is based on the Empirical Green Function (EGF) deconvolution method.
- ❖ We apply this procedure to the strongest earthquakes ($M_w \geq 4.4$) of the 2016-2017 Central Italy seismic sequence and compare our results with other studies.
- ❖ The main advantage of our method is that it is conceptually simple and fast (near real-time speeds) and can be applied to any active seismic area.

METHOD

Unilateral rupture directivity causes variations in ground motions at different azimuth around the source [Ben-Menahem, 1961]. This effect is manifested primarily by shorter-duration higher-amplitude source time functions in the direction of rupture, and longer-duration lower-amplitude source time functions in the opposite direction. In a basic model of pulse-type rupture [e.g., Haskell, 1964; Hirose and Stauder, 1965], the variations of source duration versus azimuth are given by:

$$T(\vartheta) = \frac{L}{V_r} \frac{L \cos \vartheta}{\beta} = T_0 \left(1 - \frac{V_r \cos \vartheta}{\beta} \right)$$

L = rupture length
 V_r = velocity
 β = shear wave velocity
 ϑ = angle between the rupture direction and the recording station

The parameter $T_0 = L/V_r$ corresponds to the duration of rupture propagation and is observed as source pulse duration when ϑ is $\pm 90^\circ$ (Kane et al. [2013]; Calderoni et al. [2013, 2015]).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of (a) unilateral and (b) bilateral rupture and resulting azimuthal variations of the far-field ground motion spectra at different azimuths.

For each target event we select a close EGF and compute spectral ratios at stations along forward (FW), backward (BW) and orthogonal direction (FO). For each of these station groups we compute average (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (s). According to the definition of the t-test of Ross and Ben-Zion [2016] we use the following equations to check if there is a statistically significant difference in the mean spectral amplitudes between the opposite azimuthal directions. We calculate the t-test at each frequency value using:

$$t_{ij} = \frac{\bar{X}_i - \bar{X}_j}{s_{\bar{X}_i - \bar{X}_j}} \quad s_{\bar{X}_i - \bar{X}_j} = \sqrt{\frac{s_i^2}{n_i} + \frac{s_j^2}{n_j}} \quad D_{ij} = \frac{1}{F_{\max} - F_{\min}} \int_{F_{\min}}^{F_{\max}} t_{ij}(f) df \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3 \text{ with } i \neq j$$

where \bar{X} is estimated in the range of frequency (F_{\min} ; F_{\max}), n is the number of values of the samples, and subscripts i and j refer to the sample number where 1, 2 and 3 represent FW, BW and FO, respectively. The directivity index D_{ij} is calculated as the mean of the t-test values at the i -th frequency. This procedure is performed with stations grouped within angles of $\pm 30^\circ$ from every investigated azimuthal direction. The directivity index is estimated between 0° - 180° with a step of 5° . The mean value of the spectral ratio between (F_{\min} ; F_{\max}) is indicative of the unilateral or bilateral rupture. The directivity index and the azimuth of the main rupture direction are computed as the average over target-EGF pairs applying a weighted directivity index (Table 1).

$$D_{ij} = \frac{\sum_i D_{ij}/w_k}{\sum_i 1/w_k}$$

$$Azi_{D_{ij}} = \frac{\sum_i Azi_{ij}/w_k}{\sum_i 1/w_k}$$

Table 1. Weights w_k of the directivity index D_{ij}

D_{ij}	w_k
0-1.0	0.25
1.0-1.5	0.50
1.5-3.0	0.75
>3.0	1.00

RESULTS

Example of how the procedure works for $M_w 6.0/M_L 3.1$ event pair.

Figure 2. (a) The sketch simplifies the method. (b) The map illustrates the group of stations in FW (red), BW (black) and FO (blue) directions. (c) In the top side ± 1 standard deviation band around the mean at different azimuths; in the middle side the statistical index shows the maximum value of D_{ij} ; in the bottom side the mean of the spectral ratio at different azimuths identifies unilateral or bilateral ruptures.

Figure 3. (a) Map of the study area. Stars (M_w greater than 5) and circles (M_w less than 5) symbols represent the epicenters of the seismic events analyzed in this study. The color scale of the epicenter symbols corresponds to the time evolution of the seismicity. The blue lines are the mapped normal faults from Pucci et al., 2017. The red line is the Sibillini thrust front. In the left side the beach balls represent the fault plane solutions of the M_w greater than 5. (b) Map of the seismic events analyzed in this study (circle symbols) in color scale showing the time evolution of the seismic sequence. The arrows point to the rupture propagation directions. In the inset on top the directivity index trend is shown as a function of magnitude and depth. Bottom inset reports the azimuths of the rupture propagation directions as function of the directivity index, and the rose diagram of the azimuth. (c) Redrawn from Wang et al., 2019 with overlapped directivity index greater than 4.0 (black arrows). (d) Map of the epicentral area showing main active normal faults (redrawn from Impropa et al., 2019). Yellow lines = W-dipping fault, blue lines = E-dipping faults, yellow solid lines = Laga Fault system, red solid lines = co-seismic surface rupture along the Vetore-Bove fault system, the black barbed lines = Miocene Pliocene thrust, red stars = the three mainshocks, yellow stars M5+ events. Pink arrows correspond to the directivity index greater than 4.

Figure 4. (a) Vp and Vp/Vs layers at 3- and 6-km depth (redrawn from Chiarabba et al., 2018). The aftershocks and mainshocks (stars) occurring at ± 1.5 km from each layer are shown. The gray lines are the main thrust of the system, St = Sibillini thrust modified from Bigi et al., (2011). The dashed lines are the tip of the blind ramps at depth. Magenta line is a well-resolved area. SH = Laga structural high. The seismic events analyzed in this study are superimposed on the four panels. The yellow arrows correspond to the main directions of the rupture directivity (directivity index greater than 4) and they separate the zone with high Vp/Vs (low Vs) on the right and the low Vp/Vs (high Vs) on the left. (b) Directivity index and cumulative numbers of events in the space time windows of 5 km and 2 days respectively in the forward and backward rupture directivity propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

- The presented procedure is fast and reliable.
- Applying this procedure to the 2016-2017 Central Italy seismic sequence we obtain the following findings:
 - ✓ Heterogeneity of rupture directivity is observed along the activated fault system with a complex pattern even if most of the studied events have similar focal mechanisms.
 - ✓ Homogeneous pattern in rupture directivity is observed in some areas of the activated fault system
 - ✓ A preferred trend of the rupture propagation is in large part controlled by pre-existing structural discontinuities.
 - ✓ The rupture propagation direction is mainly observed along the pre-existing structural discontinuities.
 - ✓ The interaction between fluid flow and pre-existing structural discontinuities modifying the local fault strength can be the cause of the bi-material fault interface.

RUPTURE DIRECTIVITY AND MIGRATION OF THE SEISMICITY

An important topic related to rupture directivity (Rubin and Gillard, 2000; Zaliapin and Ben-Zion, 2011; Calderoni et al., 2017), is the relationship between the direction of rupture propagation and seismicity after a main shock. We applied a quantitative method for enhancing a possible control of rupture directivity on the location of immediate aftershocks. We calculated the cumulative number of events, which occurred in the FW, BW and FO rupture propagation direction, in a radius of 5 km (Barchi et al., 2021) and a time interval of 2 days before and after the occurrence of the event (Figure 4.b). By analyzing the cumulative number of events in the two days preceding the reference event we can exclude those events occurring in areas already perturbed by previous seismicity, a condition that possibly affects the results of the analysis.

Figure 4.b shows the clustered events into 3 groups:

- Green box with a good correlation with rupture directivity and seismicity;
- Grey box with a not defined correlation due to preceding seismicity occurring in the area;
- Yellow box with no correlation.

Out of 52 analyzed events, 18 (34%) are preceded by seismicity (not defined). Of the remaining 24 events: 22 (92%) show a strong correlation between directivity and seismicity, and only 2 events (8%) do not seem to be correlated.